

Research Article

G-D's Physics Deciphers Space-Time's Geulah Driven Evolution!

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Note: *Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm based on a "time-sensitive" measurement of a predicted increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days' time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics. Dr. Bentovish's e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com.*

Abstract

Twenty-first century Theoretical Physics has reached a state of a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" signified by a basic "theoretical inconsistency" between the two "pillar" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM), as well as a principle inability to account for up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe (e.g., assumed to comprise a purely hypothetical "dark-matter" concept, but which could not be detected over the past two decades despite intensive experimental efforts!) Fortunately, a New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) entitled: the "Computational Unified Field Theory" (CUFT) also recently called: "G-D's Physics" has been discovered which was shown capable of resolving this apparent GRT-QM "theoretical inconsistency" and also offer an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the accelerated expansion of the universe (which discards the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" concept as "superfluous", i.e., "non-existent")! This New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is based on the discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe for every consecutive "Universal Frame" (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ")! Accordingly, a new "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) was discovered which completely integrates (for the first time in Physics) the four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") as well as between GRT & QM! Indeed, the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete "dissolution" of the entire universe "in-between" two (such) consecutive UF's frames has led to the recognition of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm as negating the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" (relativistic or quantum) physical interaction/s existing in any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s! Empirical Validation of two unique "G-D's Physics" "Critical Predictions" has been demonstrated in this article, thereby substantiating it as the New (satisfactory) Twenty-First Century's Scientific Paradigm! This New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm offers an alternative theoretical explanation for the evolution of "Space-Time" - as governed by the UCP's "Preplanned Blueprint Plan" of advancing the universe from its initial "inanimate matter" state through subsequent "animate": plants, animals and human-beings - and leading up to the "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" of the universe in which Science and Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCP alongside its intrinsic (sublime) characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" (which will also typify Humanity's behavior accordingly)!

Introduction

Currently, there exists a basic Paradigmatic-Crisis in the foundations of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM), signified by an apparent theoretical inconsistency that exists between them, and a principle inability of this Old Paradigm to account for up to 95% of all the mass in the universe - i.e., assumed to comprise a purely hypothetical "dark-matter" concept which is assumed to "cause" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion, but which cannot be detected experimentally (for the past two full decades, despite numerous attempts to do so)! Given this key unresolved "enigma" of the "unexplained" accelerated rate of the universe's expansion (assumed to be explained by the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" concept but which cannot be detected empirically), the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's Einstein's Equations Model - explaining the evolution of Space-Time, as "caused" by this purely hypothetical "dark-matter" concept must be questioned!

Hence, what ensues is an attempt to rectify this "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm through the discovery of a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) of "G-D's Physics" (e.g., the "Computational Unified Field Theory"), which also offers a new alternative (and exciting) explanation for this evolution of "Space-Time" - based on the discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP), which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ", thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every such "minimal time-point"! indeed, "G-D's Physics" discovery of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP's (extremely rapid: " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (as the series of UF's frames) was shown capable of resolving the (apparent) "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM!

Nevertheless, according to Thomas Kuhn's (famous) analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" (1962) [1-51], it becomes clear that in order

for the general scientific community to accept “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) as a satisfactory NSP, it is necessary for “G-D’s Physics” NSP to identify at least one (unique) “Critical Prediction” that differentiates it from the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm! Indeed, what follows is an experimental description of two such (unique) “Critical Predictions” differentiating the NSP of “G-D’s Physics” from the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, and their empirical validation – e.g., pertaining to the “Proton Radius Puzzle” findings and also pertaining to “G-D’s Physics’ unique prediction of a “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE) (as opposed to the “constant rate” of the universe’s expansion predicted by GRT)! Obviously, to the extent that these two unique “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” will be shown to be experimentally validated, then this will lead to an unequivocal acceptance of “G-D’s Physics” as the NSP (satisfactory) for Twenty-First Century’s Theoretical Physics!

One of the key discoveries stipulated by this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm is the existence of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe – at the incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec”! thereby producing an incredibly rapid series of “Universal Frames” (UF’s) comprising the entire physical universe at every minimal time-point.

Indeed, one of the key differences between the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm and the New “G-D’s Physics’ A-Causal Computation” Paradigm is the fundamental realization, whereby there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF’s frame/s! Rather, the sole manner in which the entire physical universe (e.g., or indeed any smaller “Physical System” found within this physical universe) “exists” and “evolves” – is solely based on this singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) production of the (extremely rapid) series of UF’s frame/s! Thus, for instance, previous articles have indicated that this New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm negated (in principle) the feasibility of GRT’s “Big-Bang Model”! This is because since this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (e.g., for each consecutive UF’s frame/s), therefore there cannot exist any direct (or even indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any (consecutive) UF’s frame/s! Moreover, since all of these exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any consecutive UF’s frame/s “dissolve” back into the singularity of this UCP “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s, therefore, there also cannot exist any such “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in different UF’s frame/s! Hence, the basic “Big-Bang” Model of GRT assuming that an initial Big-Bang “nuclear event” “caused” the creation of all of the “matter”, “energy”, “space”, “time”, all of the galaxies, stars, planets etc. in the universe is strictly negated by the New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm!

Hence, we see that according to “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – either “during” any consecutive UF’s frame/s or “in-between” them! Moreover, according to two profound new Theoretical Postulates of this New “G-D’s Physics” Paradigm, entitled: the “Computational Invariance Principle” and the (closely related) “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR) the only “constant”, “uniform” and “continuous” principle that exists both “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s, and also exists “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frames is this singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP/UCR) that manifests as the physical universe “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s, but remains solely and singularly “in-between” any two UF’s frame/s!

Indeed, it may be said that there is a stark contrast between the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm (e.g., underlying both GRT & QM) and the New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm in terms of their basic assumption regarding the origin- true nature- and “purpose”- of the existence of the entire physical universe! According to the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, the origination of the entire physical universe is assumed to have been “caused” by a (random) initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event, it evolves merely based on (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between certain “massive objects” and their assumed “causing” of a “curvature of Space-Time” (and conversely, the determination of the “travelling pathways” of these “massive objects” and other “less-massive” objects is strictly “caused” by this “curvature of Space-Time”); and it “drifting” towards an “Entropic State” of a complete “dissolution” of the entire physical universe, and all of its Suns, Galaxies, planets etc.... In contrast, according to the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm, the entire origination- and continuous “dissolution”, re-creation and evolution of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the physical universe has been “pre-planned”, and evolved based on the “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle’s” (UCP) plan to evolve the universe from its initial “inanimate matter” state through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Ultimate “Perfected Geulah State” in which the singularity of this “All-Goodness”, “Moral”, “Peace” and “Harmony” (characterized) UCR will be recognized by Science and Humanity, thereby leading Humanity towards this “Perfected Geulah State” of Humanity and the universe, in which Humanity will lead a life characterized by these (“sublime”) characteristics of “Morality”, “Goodness”, “Peace” and “Harmony”!

“G-D’s Physics” Twenty-First Century’s Paradigmatic-Shift

Scientific Inquiry (within any given discipline) is governed by empirical data and logical reasoning that can best explain that given data within a cohesive Theoretical Framework! However, the famous Philosopher of Science, Thomas Kuhn taught us that the evolution of such Scientific Inquiry (within a given scientific discipline) alternates between phases governed by a given “Standard Paradigm” in which such a given “Standard Paradigm” is capable of explaining all known data and phenomena, and an inevitable subsequent “Paradigmatic-Shift” into a “New Scientific Paradigm” (NSP) which follows the appearance of a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” within the Old “Standard Paradigm”; Such a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” is characterized by the appearance of “theoretical inconsistencies” between the “foundations” of the Old “Standard Paradigm”, such as for instance the apparent theoretical inconsistency that appeared between Newtonian Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory. In addition, a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” is also characterized by the principle inability of this Old “Standard Paradigm” to account for a key empirical phenomenon, such the inability of the Old 19th century’s Newtonian Mechanics to empirically validate the existence of the purely hypothetical “Ether” concept which was key for Newtonian Mechanical Theoretical Framework?! Kuhn teaches us that alongside with the appearance of such a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” for the Old “Standard Paradigm” (in this case Newtonian Mechanics) there emerges the “New Paradigm” (e.g., Relativity Theory) shown capable of resolving the apparent “theoretical inconsistency” (between Newtonian Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory), resolving the “unexplained empirical phenomenon” (e.g., Relativity Theory discarded the purely hypothetical “Ether” concept as “superfluous” or “non-existent”!); and most significantly identify and empirically validate at least one unique “Critical Prediction” of the “New Paradigm” – as more valid than the corresponding prediction of the “Old Paradigm”: In the case of Einstein’s General Relativity Theory (GRT) this unique “Critical Prediction” related to his prediction regarding the double-valued curvature of Mercury’s perihelion’s pathway around the Sun (e.g., due to the Sun’s mass’ curvature of Space-Time affecting Mercury’s curved perihelion pathway); Indeed, once Einstein’s double-valued Mercury’s perihelion pathway (around the Sun) unique “Critical Prediction” was validated by Eddington during the famous 1919 Solar Eclipse – Einstein’s GRT “triumphed” and was accepted as the New Scientific Paradigm for 20th century Theoretical Physics!

We stand at an equivalent (historic) "junction" in which the Old "Material-Causal" (Standard Paradigm) of GRT and Quantum Mechanics (QM), has reached a clear "Paradigmatic-Crisis", e.g., due the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between these two GRT & QM "pillars" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm seem "theoretically inconsistent": this is due to the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT's strict insistence upon the "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) for the transmission of any signal (or information) across space and time, as opposed to QM's (empirically validated) "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon which indicates that a measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects the other "entangled particle's" complimentary (space-energy, time-mass) value/s, e.g., apparently contradicting GRT's SLB fundamental constraint?! Additionally, there exists a key "unexplained empirical phenomenon" relating to the universe's accelerated rate of expansion which can only be explained by GRT's assuming of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts which are assumed to comprise up to 90% of all the mass and energy in the universe – but yet failed to be detected (despite numerous experimental attempts) for the past two decades?! Indeed, two highly influential scientific articles recently published by Scientific American begin questioning the validity of these purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts! (REF??). Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT and QM has reached a state of "Paradigmatic-Crisis" which has indeed led to the discovery of a New "Computational Unified Field Theory" (CUFT), recently termed: "G-D's Physics" (See exhaustive Bentovish References) shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM!

The manner in which this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is able to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM is based on its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which is postulated to simultaneously compute all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, e.g., including their four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – at an unfathomably rapid rate of "c2/h" = 1.36-50 (sec)! This produces an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at every such "minimal time point", e.g., with all such exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames! Additionally, as part of the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s, it also computes "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) relativistic "object" or subatomic "particle" computation, as well as "Multi Spatial-Temporal" (MST) computation of more than one spatial-temporal "object"/"particle" point at any given UF's frame/s, e.g., giving rise to the (relativistic or subatomic) "wave" phenomenon! Thus, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm's theoretical framework is capable of explicating the embedding of any SSP "particle", e.g., including two "entangled particles" as integral parts of the broader "MST" "wave" phenomenon – which are both embedded within the "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" (EST) UCP's computation of the entire UF's frame/s (e.g., for each consecutive UF's frame)! Viewed from this novel higher-ordered perspective of the UCP's EST computation of all exhaustive spatial temporal pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) – as embedding within it both the SST "entangled particles" and the broader MST "wave" computation allows for this New "G-D's Physics" to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM – while pointing at the much more exhaustive theoretical framework of the UCP's production of the series of UF's frame/s!

Indeed, a major discovery made by this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is the complete unification – not only between GRT & QM, but also between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (as well as between the four basic Forces!) within a new-

ly discovered "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), which explicates the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! This major UCF discovery stems from "G-D's Physics" novel computation of these four basic physical features as underlie by the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency": According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm the UCP computes for each given (relativistic or subatomic) object – its degree of "Consistency" (e.g., "consistent" or "inconsistent") relative to two possible "Framework" levels, i.e., relative to the entire "frame" or relative to the "object" itself (i.e., internal composition), which gives rise to those four basic physical features; That is, when the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" measures of any given object this yields the two corresponding physical features of "space" and "energy", whereas when the UCP computes the two "Object" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" measures this produces the two corresponding physical features of "mass" and "time"! Based on these new (and exciting) UCP's computational definitions of these four basic physical features (given below) the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm was able to integrate them as secondary computational features of the same singular higher-ordered UCP, thereby giving rise to this profound novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF)!

THE "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} \text{UF's } \{n \dots n \dots n\} [Px]_{(a \dots z)} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

Note: which is accompanied by "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) computational (previous) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" as representing "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computational properties of the UCP's simultaneous and integrated computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels:

$$S: (f\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] + \dots f\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)] \leq f\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i \dots n)]$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: (f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i..n)]$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \Sigma[O_{\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] = O_{(i..n)\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} \{UF(i..n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_{\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i..n) \leq n * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \Sigma[O_{\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O_{(i..n)\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} \{UF(i..n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$$

such that:

$$T: [O_{\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i..n) \leq c * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Significantly, it has been previously shown that this novel UCF possesses two equivalent "Relativistic Format" and "Quantum Format" which indicate that it embeds (within it) "special-cases" of well-known physical laws and characteristics of GRT such as the "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ("E = Mc²") and QM's "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" "complimentary pairs"; thereby pointing at "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's complete unification- embedding- and indeed transcending- of GRT & QM! However, since one of the key Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe including all of these exhaustive spatial pixels – "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames; therefore, the

New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm has been characterized as an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! This is because due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and its complete "dissolution" "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames (e.g., back into the UCP's singular existence), there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s!

In fact, due to the only "transient" and "phenomenal" existence of any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, e.g., which exists only "during" the UCP's production of every consecutive UF's frame/s, but "ceases to exist" and "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frames, two additional profound Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm, termed: the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" postulate: a) That the only "computationally-invariant" principle in the universe which exists both "during" the UCP's successive computation of each subsequent UF's frame/s, and solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) is this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP); as opposed to the only "transient-phenomenal" appearance of the entire physical universe – regarded as "computationally-variant", e.g., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed or produced by this singular UCP) but "dissolving" back into the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; b) Therefore, there only exists one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists uniformly, continuously and constantly – both "during" its manifestation as the physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), and also exists singularly "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe)!

Viewed from this new (higher, more exhaustive) perspective of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a series of additional (profound) associated Theoretical Postulates have been discovered, including: c) The "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: hypothesizing that since there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s, the only manner in which this series of UF's frames (comprising the entire physical universe) could "evolve" is based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's "pre-planning" of the entire evolution- (or manifestation-) of the whole universe from "inanimate matter" through "animate": "plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards", i.e., based on the UCP's "pre-planning" of the whole evolution of all "inanimate" and "animate" forms leading up to this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! A Metaphor regarding "King Solomon's" build-up of the Divine Temple was utilized to explain this "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: that is, in the same way that Kin Solomon must have received a completed "Perfected Blue-Print Plan" of the "Ultimate Completed Temple State" (e.g., and all of the necessary "steps" required to reach this "Ultimate Completed Temple State" – prior to his various builders starting to construct this immaculate Divine Temple, so it is postulated that the UCP/UCR must have "pre-planned" the whole evolution of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter", "animate": plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" – through the entire evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, ultimately leading to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", i.e., in which Science and the whole of Humanity will recognize the singular existence of this higher-ordered UCR, alongside the recognition of its basic characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. (previously delineated).

Method & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \Sigma\{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: \{O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i) - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n)\} \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [55,57].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction [55,57], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \Sigma\{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent",

i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" [50], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction, [54,58], higher dimension gravity, [49], a new boson, [53], and the quasi-free hypothesis $\pi+$ [52], and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashanah" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)?! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar

Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Hence, to the extent that these two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm are empirically validated, then this will convince the Scientific Community that the New "G-D's Physics" has to be accepted as a satisfactory New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics! Based on such direct empirical validation of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a discussion ensues of the manner in which "G-D's Physics" newly discovered singular higher-ordered Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) is capable of computing every exhaustive spatial pixel or "object" (e.g., including "human-beings" as opposed to "non-human": "inanimate" material object/s, as well as "animate": plants and animals) – based on a further discovery of the UCP's "Gimateria" (i.e., Hebrew letters' numerical values) of each object's five "secondary-essential" "Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (HCD's) of: "Chessed", "Gevurah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod" (e.g., each of them comprising "ten zero's" out of the "fifty zero's" comprising the incredible rate of the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe: "c2/h" = 1.36-50 (sec)! As will be discussed, this entirely new conception of the manner in which this singular, higher-ordered UCP computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's "object" in the universe is "non-material", i.e., exemplifying the "translation" of the fundamental new "building-blocks" ("or "Atoms" – metaphorically) of the entire physical universe from the Hebrew letters' "Gimatria" (numerical values, also associated with these five "secondary-essential" HCD's corresponding "ten zero's") to the production of each ("human" or "non-human") object's unique physical characteristics! Indeed, it is shown that this novel manner in which the UCP is seen to compute the specific physical characteristics of each individual (unique "human" or "non-human") "object" is a part and parcel of the UCP's overall "Blueprint Plan" of steering the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate" material composition through its "animate": "plants", "animals", human-beings – leading to the fulfillment of the UCP's "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of a "Moral", "Spiritual" and even "Physical" "Perfected" state of the universe in which the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), e.g., characterized by "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" being recognized (and accepted) by Science and Humanity (more generally)!

Discussion

Hence, we see that those two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" NSP have been empirically validated, therefore substantiating "G-D's Physics" as a (satisfactory) New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics! It is nevertheless, important to note, that this NSP includes the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's two "foundations" of GRT & QM as integral parts (e.g., "special-cases") within the (broader) theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" discovery of a (novel) "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) – which also completely unifies (e.g., for the first time in Physics) between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (e.g., as secondary computational features of this singular higher-ordered UCP!)

THE "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{array} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m} \quad \text{UF's } \{n \dots n \dots n\} [Px]_{[a \dots z]}$$

Note: which is accompanied by "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) computational (previous) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" as representing "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computational properties of the UCP's simultaneous and integrated computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels:

$$S: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] \leq f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i \dots n)]$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: (f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i \dots n)]$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \sum [O_{i\{0-x,0-y,0-z\}} [UF(n)] = O_{i \dots n\{0-x,0-y,0-z\}} \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {0-x,0-y,0-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i...n)] \leq n * h \{[UF's(i...n)]\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] \neq O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i...n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i...n)\}]$$

such that:

$$T: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i...n)] \leq c * h \{[UF's(i...n)]\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Significantly, it has been previously shown that this novel UCF possesses two equivalent "Relativistic Format" and "Quantum Format" which indicate that it embeds (within it) "special-cases" of well-known physical laws and characteristics of GRT such as the "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ("E = Mc²") and QM's "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" "complimentary pairs"; thereby pointing at "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's complete unification- embedding- and indeed transcending- of GRT & QM! However, since one of the key Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe including all of these exhaustive spatial pixels – "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames; therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm has been characterized as an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! This is because due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and its complete "dissolution" "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames (e.g., back into the UCP's singular existence), there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s!

In fact, due to the only "transient" and "phenomenal" existence of any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, e.g., which exists only "during" the UCP's production of every consecutive UF's frame/s, but "ceases to exist" and "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frames, two additional profound Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm, termed: the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" postulate: a) That the only "computationally-invariant" principle in the universe which exists both "during" the UCP's successive computation of each subsequent UF's frame/s, and solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) is this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP); as opposed to the only "transient-phenomenal" appearance of the entire physical universe – regarded as "computationally-variant", e.g., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed or produced by this singular UCP) but "dissolving" back into the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's

frame/s; b) Therefore, there only exists one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists uniformly, continuously and constantly – both "during" its manifestation as the physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), and also exists singularly "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe)!

Viewed from this new (higher, more exhaustive) perspective of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a series of additional (profound) associated Theoretical Postulates have been discovered, including: c) The "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: hypothesizing that since there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s, the only manner in which this series of UF's frames (comprising the entire physical universe) could "evolve" is based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's "pre-planning" of the entire evolution- (or manifestation-) of the whole universe from "inanimate matter" through "animate": "plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards", i.e., based on the UCP's "pre-planning" of the whole evolution of all "inanimate" and "animate" forms leading up to this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! A Metaphor regarding "King Solomon's" build-up of the Divine Temple was utilized to explain this "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: that is, in the same way that Kin Solomon must have received a completed "Perfected Blue-Print Plan" of the "Ultimate Completed Temple State" (e.g., and all of the necessary "steps" required to reach this "Ultimate Completed Temple State" – prior to his various builders starting to construct this immaculate Divine Temple, so it is postulated that the UCP/UCR must have "pre-planned" the whole evolution of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter", "animate": plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" – through the entire evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, ultimately leading to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", i.e., in which Science and the whole of Humanity will recognize the singular existence of this higher-ordered UCR, alongside the recognition of its basic characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. (previously delineated).

A Brief Summary of "G-D's Physics" additional Theoretical Postulates is outlined (in order to provide an exhaustive summary of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm):

d) The UCP's Three Computational Dimensions:

Indeed, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers a new (and exciting) theoretical explanation for the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on two out of its three hypothesized "Computational Dimensions", e.g., "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent"); According to "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, the UCP simultaneously computes for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe these four basic physical features based on particular computational combinations, e.g., an "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computation derives the two (corresponding) physical features of "mass" and "time", whereas the UCP's computation of any given object's "Frame" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" values yields its "space" and "energy" characteristics!

"G-D's Physics" has also been shown to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM based on the discovery of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that simultaneously computes (for all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe, at every "minimal time-point") the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time",

thereby producing the extremely rapid (e.g., $c^2/h = 1.36\text{-}50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$) series of those “Universal Frames”(UF’s, comprising the entire physical universe – at every such “minimal time-point”)!

The “Computational Invariance Principle” and “Universal Consciousness Reality” Postulates

Indeed, over and beyond the (extremely) significant discovery- and empirical validation- of “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) of Twenty-First Century’s Theoretical Physics, “G-D’s Physics” completely revises our most basic understanding and appreciation of the origin- nature- evolution- and even “Ultimate Goal” of the entire physical universe, e.g., and of our own very significant role within it as human-beings (and Science and Humanity in general)! In order to fully appreciate “G-D’s Physics” NSP’s new understanding of the physical universe, let’s reexamine two of its (profound) new Theoretical Postulates, termed: the “Computational Invariance Principle” and “Universal Consciousness Reality”! According to the “Computational Invariance Principle”, since only this singular higher-ordered UCP remains “constant”, “continuous” “uniform” – both “during” its (simultaneous) computation of each consecutive UF’s frame/s’ exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features (of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time”), and also solely remains (e.g., without the presence of any physical universe “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s); whereas the four physical features of every exhaustive spatial pixel (comprising the entire physical universe, for each consecutive UF’s frame/s) “exist” only “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s (as solely computed based on the UCP) – but “dissolves” back into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s; therefore only this singular (higher-ordered) UCP may be considered as “computationally invariant”, e.g., exists “constantly”, “continuously” and “uniformly” both “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s and “in-between” them, whereas the four basic physical features comprising every exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) may only be considered as “computationally-variant”, e.g., existing only “during” each consecutive UF’s frame, but “ceases to exist” (e.g., “dissolving” into the singularity of the UCP) “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s!

Therefore, the (closely associated) “Universal Consciousness Reality” theoretical postulate reasons that since only this singular higher-ordered UCP is “computationally invariant” (existing both “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s – and computing each exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe), whereas the entire physical universe’s exhaustive spatial pixels represents only a “transient” and “phenomenal” manifestation of this singular UCP (e.g., existing only “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s as solely computed by this singular UCP but not “in-between” them); hence, the only singular “reality” (that truly “exists”) is this singular UCP, e.g., which exists both “during” its computation of each consecutive UF’s frame/s and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s, whereas the entire physical universe – only represents a “transient-phenomenal” manifestation of this singular UCP; and may therefore be termed: the “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR), which exists “constantly”, “uniformly” and “continuously” both “during its production of each consecutive UF’s frame/s and also (solely) exists “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s!

Alongside this profound new realization of these two (profound) “Computational Invariance Principle” and “Universal Consciousness Reality” theoretical postulates, the new “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm was also termed: an “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm, signifying its principle (basic) negation of the possibility of any (direct or even indirect) “material-causal” physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same-or different- UF’s frame/s! This is (once again) due to the “simultaneity” if the UCP’s computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any consecutive UF’s frame/s – which

negates the possibility of any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any (single) UF’s frame/s; and since all of the exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any (consecutive) UF’s frame/s “dissolve” (back into the singularity of this UCP) “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s, therefore there cannot exist any (such) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels “across” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s! Hence, we realize, that the entire physical universe does not operate based on any relativistic or (subatomic) quantum (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels but is rather governed- and operated- solely based on the singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR)!

Negation of the “Big-Bang Model” & “Einstein’s Equations’ Material-Causal Assumption”!

Indeed, once we begin realizing that the entire physical universe exists only as a “transient-phenomenal” manifestation of this singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR) (e.g., since it only exists “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s as solely computed by this singular UCR but “dissolves” back into the UCR’s singularity “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s); and that (in fact) there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any (two or more) relativistic or quantum (subatomic) exhaustive spatial pixels (found within the same-or different- UF’s frame/s); we have to revise some of the basic “material-causal” assumptions standing as the very “basis” of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM!

Thus, for instance, the basic “Big-Bang” Model of GRT, which assumes that the entire physical universe was “caused” or “created” by an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event that created all of the suns, galaxies, “matter” and “energy” (“space” and “time”) of the entire physical universe – was shown to be questioned and (in fact) negated by the New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm! This is simply because if (indeed) this singular (higher-ordered) UCR simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., at the “unfathomable” rate of $c^2/h = 1.36\text{-}50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$), and “dissolves” back into the UCR singularity “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s, then there could not have been any (direct or even indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the first- second-... or “trillionth” UF’s frame/s – which implies that the “Big-Bang” nuclear event could not have occurred, i.e., at least as “causing” the creation of all the suns, galaxies, “matter” and “energy” etc. in the universe! The only thing that could have happened is the UCR’s consecutive computation of a series of UF’s frames that evolved- and is (in fact) still evolving the entire physical universe (and every exhaustive spatial pixel/s comprising it) – e.g., from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: “plants”, “animals” and “human-beings” towards the “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal” of the universe, in which Science and Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCR, alongside its “intrinsic sublime” characteristics of “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”!

In order to better grasp this new “A-Causal Computation” “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm a “Cinematic-Film Metaphor” has been illustrated: depicting an imaginary “film-scenario”, in which a “mercury-ball” is shown to impact a “glass-jar” (filled with water) which seems to “cause” the breakage of this “glass-jar” (and consequent “spillage of water”) ... But (in fact), when we “slow-down” (and even “halt”) the progression of this “Cinematic-Film Metaphor”, and closely examine each of these consecutive “film-frames” (separately), we can clearly discern that at each (consecutive) film-frame, all of its exhaustive spatial pixels are being depicted “simultaneously” – so that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal physical interaction” between any two (or more) spatial pixels comprising each of these (consecutive) film-frames! We also realize that

there cannot exist any such “material-causal physical interaction” between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two consecutive film-frames (e.g., or in fact any two film-frames)! This is simply due to the fact that “in-between” any two such film-frames transpires a “pure-light” (of the “projector”) so that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “physical interaction” between any of the (exhaustive) spatial pixels comprising one “film-frame” and any other subsequent “film-frame”! Therefore, we realize that despite the “appearance” of a “material-causal” physical interaction between the “mercury ball” and its apparent “impact” upon the “glass-jar” – which seemed to “cause” the “breakage” of this “glass-jar” (and “spillage” of water); the only thing that really “exists” is the arrangement of this series of “film-frames” depicting an (ever-closer) “proximity” of the “mercury ball” and “glass-jar” until their “conjoining” (e.g., being presented as “touching” each other) which then leads to the presentation of a broken “glass-jar” and “spillage of water”... Hence, we must realize that despite the appearance of a direct “material-causal” physical interaction between the “mercury-ball” and (“water-filled”) “glass-jar” (which seems to “cause” the “breakage” of this “glass-jar” - and “spillage” of “water”) – in reality, there is only an “arrangement” of this series of “film-frames” in a manner which gives us the “impression” (or “perception”) of such a “material-causal” relationship between the “mercury-ball” and its “breakage” of the “glass-jar”...

Indeed, based on this (simple yet profound) “Cinematic-Film Metaphor” we can clearly understand that in the same manner that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in (any) two film-frames (e.g., due to the “simultaneous” presentation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given “film-frame” and the complete “dissolution” of all the exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given “film-frame/s” into the “pure-light” separating between any two such consecutive “film-frames”); there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (“consecutive” or even “non-consecutive”) “universal Frames” (comprising the entire physical universe at any given “minimal time-point”)! Therefore, the “material-causal” assumption underlying the “Big-Bang” Model (emanating from Einstein’s GRT) is strictly negated based on this New Twenty-First Century’s “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm! This is (once again) simply because this “Big-Bang Model” precisely assumes such “material-causal” (direct) physical interactions between an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event and its “causing” (or “creation”) of all the “suns”, “galaxies”, “matter” and “energy” (“space” and “time”) in the physical universe – which is strictly negated by “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any (consecutive) UF’s (and the complete “dissolution” of all of these exhaustive spatial pixels into the singularity of the “Universal Computational Reality”, “UCR” “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s!)

A Geulah-Driven Space-Time Evolution of the Universe!

What (then) is the alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation of “G-D’s Physics” New (Twenty-First Century) Scientific Paradigm for the (ongoing) accelerated expansion of the entire physical universe? In order to fully understand (and appreciate) the “simplicity” (and “elegance”) of “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) New “A-Causal Computation” theoretical explanation of the accelerated expansion of the universe based on this singular higher-ordered UCR, we must (first) describe its “Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions” (THCD’s) (and associated THCD’s-Universal Computational Formula):

The Universal Consciousness Reality’s (UCR) “Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions”:

1) The UCR’s “Wisdom/Free-Will” Hierarchical Computational Dimension (“חכמה”):

The UCP’s first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP’s “Wisdom/Free-Will” which relates to the UCP’s complete “Free-Will” in its computation and “laws” pertaining to the successive computation- “dissolution” re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any “material-causal” physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR’s “Free-Will/Wisdom” Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a “Free-Will/Wisdom” of the UCR’s initial conception of the creation of an apparently “separate” and “independent” physical universe – which seems to exist “independently” of the UCR’s sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate “Goal” of creating Human-Beings possessing the most “expansive” form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and “All-Goodwill” characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP’s initial impetus and Wisdom’s conception of the possibility of creating an apparently “independent” physical universe (e.g., from its true sole “Universal Consciousness Reality’s” sustenance of it) that will “evolve” the most “expansive” form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR’s “Infinite Wisdom”, “All-Goodness” characteristics!

2) The UCP’s “All-Goodness/Computation” Hierarchical Dimension (“בינה”):

The UCP’s secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of “All-Goodness/Computation” (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR’s “Hierarchical Computational Plan” execution of this initial “Free-Will/Wisdom” general conception of the creation of an apparently “independent” physical universe that evolves into Humanity’s ultimate “Geulah” State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR’s “All-Goodness” characteristics: This secondary “All-Goodness/Computation” Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP’s principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time”, which allows for the creation of apparently “independent” “living-organisms”, e.g., each possessing varying degrees of “awareness” or “Consciousness”, and existing apparently “independent” of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!?! Indeed, it is this apparent “independence” of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR) which manifests the UCR’s “All-Goodness” benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- “dissolving”- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more “expansive” form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR’s “Reversed-Time Geulah Goal” Hierarchical Computational Dimension (“Daat”/ דעת):

The UCR’s fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the “Reversed-Time ‘Geulah’ Goal” which describes (for the first time in the UCR’s successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR’s full-complete “Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan” for creating and “evolving” the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more “expansive” forms of Consciousness, i.e., from “inanimate”, “animate”: plants, animals, human-beings and up to the “Ultimate Geulah Goal” of Humanity’s (and Science’s) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR’s entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more “expansive” forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate “matter”, through “animate”: plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most “expansive” form of “Collective Human Consciousness” recognizing and leading a “Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State”: in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR) including the basic, “Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral

Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past"- "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blueprint", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ תעד) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חסד"/Chessed):

This "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/ חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah " may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has

been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Devorah"/(גבורה):

Denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/Tiferet):

The sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th , 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings –

as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תראפת"/Tiferet which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "נצח"/"Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva" (תשובה) "Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva" / "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make

a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "יסוד"/"Yessod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"היכלם"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yessod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר"/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כתר"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")); This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ (sec) for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the “Ultimate Goal” of the entire physical universe’s development is given through “G-D’s Physics” newly discovered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another “Solomon’s Temple Blueprint Plan” Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has “preplanned” the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the “Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal”, in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”!

According to this “Solomon’s Temple Blueprint Plan” Metaphor, King Solomon had to “preplan” the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its “Completed-Perfected-Final” stage – “backwards” towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this “Blueprint Plan” will lead up to this “Completed-Perfected-Final” state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon’s builders begin “constructing” this Immaculate Temple – without such a “perfected Blueprint Plan”, i.e., just by “experimenting” with different stones with no “preplanned Blueprint Plan” for its orderly completion?!) Equivalently, “G-D’s Physics” New (Twenty-First Century’s) “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has “preplanned” a “Blueprint Plan” – from the “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State” “backwards” towards the initial stages of “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the “Perfected Geulah State” of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any “material-causal” physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive UF’s frame/s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be “caused” by any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between certain “massive” objects and their (assumed) “curvature” of “Space-Time” (or the corresponding determination of the “travelling pathways” of these “massive” or other “less-massive” objects as “caused” by this assumed “curved Space-Time” fabric, as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe is being continuously “created”, “dissolved”, “re-created” and “evolved” so many “trillions” of time each second –by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned “Blueprint Plan” of advancing the universe towards its “Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal” State! Indeed, we currently stand at a “historic time”, e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington’s empirical validation of Einstein’s GRT’s “Critical Prediction” of Mercury’s “double-valued” perihelion’s curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT’s & QM’s Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity’s (and Science’s) “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal” State! This is because the very definition of this “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal” State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” – which will also characterize (“guide” and “typify”) Humanity’s newly “Perfected Geulah State”!

Dedication

This (profound) article is solely dedicated to my Dear Beloved (diseased) Mother, Dr. Tirzah Bentwich (bat Yitzchak) whose encouragement has allowed me to discover this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm that may uplift Science and Humanity towards its realization of the “Perfected Geulah Goal State” of the Universe!

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